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**Title: Quantum Artificial Intelligence in Galactic Cosmic Ray
Intensity Forecasting**

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Abstract:

The galactic cosmic rays are energetic charged particles originated from outside the solar system which arrive at the Earth, as an effect of the changes of the interplanetary magnetic field because of the solar cycle. In this study, a Quantum Artificial Intelligence methodology is proposed in order to predict galactic cosmic ray intensity by taking into consideration the solar activity regarding the number of the sunspots. Different number of qubits were applied to achieve the optimal results. The Quantum Machine Learning model was constructed by developing a quantum circuit with several quantum gates. The proposed model was trained by implementing the gradient descent algorithm. The cosmic ray data were retrieved from Neutron Monitor Database (NMDB), collected by the Earth neutron monitor stations. The final results of the research have shown a very good prediction accuracy of the galactic cosmic ray intensity.